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DEVELOPING GESTURES IN THE INFANT CLASSROOM: FROM SHOWING AND GIVING TO POINTING.

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	Comunidad de Madrid (SI2/PBG/2020-00016)	Dr. María Núñez
Abstract:	<p>Research on gesture development has mostly focused on home environments. Little is known about early communicative development in other relevant contexts, such as early-year-schools. These settings, rich in diverse educative situations, objects, and communicative partners, provide a contrast to parent–child interactions, complementing our understanding of gesture development.</p> <p>This study aims to describe the development of the first gestures in the infant classrooms of early-years-schools, focusing on ostensive gestures of showing and giving—their emergence, communicative functions, and relation to the subsequent emergence of pointing.</p> <p>We conducted a longitudinal, observational investigation analyzing the gestures of 21 children (7-13 months). Over seven months, we observed and registered children’s daily interactions in the classroom, employing a mixed quantitative and qualitative approach to analyze the types and functions of their gestures.</p> <p>We found a significant increase and diversification of gesture types and functions with age. Gestures followed a proximal–distal developmental course. Ostensive gestures were the earliest and most prevalent gestures observed. There was a correlation between the frequency of these gestures, with ostensive gestures fulfilling communicative functions later observed in pointing. Our qualitative analysis revealed the progressive construction of ostensive gestures into spontaneous, complex, and conventional forms of communication.</p> <p>These results highlight the important role of ostensive gestures in early communicative development, paving the way for distal communication through pointing and relating to the origin of intentional communication. More broadly, these findings have significant implications for early educational practices and show the value of conducting research on developmental processes in early education.</p>	

DEVELOPING GESTURES IN THE INFANT CLASSROOM: FROM SHOWING AND GIVING TO POINTING.

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3. Statements and Declarations

Declaration of Competing Interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper, either directly or indirectly.

Human Ethics and Consent to Participate Declarations: This study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and the Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 on Personal Data Protection and the Guarantee of Digital Rights. Before data collection, written informed consent was obtained from the main caregivers

of the children, their teachers, and the principals of each early years school involved in the study. The research ethics committee of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid approved the objectives and procedures of this investigation (Reference CEI-1132238). All privacy rights were meticulously observed, and to ensure confidentiality, the names of the schools, children, and teachers have been anonymized.

Consent to Publish Declaration: In accordance with the guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and the Spanish Organic Law 15/1999 on the Protection of Personal Data, explicit consent was obtained from caregivers, teachers, and schools to publish images showing the faces of the participants, including both teachers and children, for academic and educational purposes. This consent covers the use of any images where potential human faces are detected. All participants were informed about the purpose of the images and the contexts in which they will be used, ensuring that they understood and agreed to these conditions.

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ABSTRACT

Research on gesture development has mostly focused on home environments. Little is known about early communicative development in other relevant contexts, such as early-year-schools. These settings, rich in diverse educative situations, objects, and communicative partners, provide a contrast to parent–child interactions, complementing our understanding of gesture development.

This study aims to describe the development of the first gestures in the infant classrooms of early-years-schools, focusing on ostensive gestures of showing and giving—their emergence, communicative functions, and relation to the subsequent emergence of pointing.

We conducted a longitudinal, observational investigation analyzing the gestures of 21 children (7-13 months). Over seven months, we observed and registered children’s daily interactions in the classroom, employing a mixed quantitative and qualitative approach to analyze the types and functions of their gestures.

We found a significant increase and diversification of gesture types and functions with age. Gestures followed a proximal–distal developmental course. Ostensive gestures were the earliest and most prevalent gestures observed. There was a correlation between the frequency of these gestures, with ostensive gestures fulfilling communicative functions later observed in pointing. Our qualitative analysis revealed

the progressive construction of ostensive gestures into spontaneous, complex, and conventional forms of communication.

These results highlight the important role of ostensive gestures in early communicative development, paving the way for distal communication through pointing and relating to the origin of intentional communication. More broadly, these findings have significant implications for early educational practices and show the value of conducting research on developmental processes in early education.

Keywords: Gesture development; Early Childhood Education; Showing; Giving; Pointing; Infancy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Before language becomes the primary tool of meaning, gestures are early semiotic systems through which children intentionally communicate, understand the world, and control their behavior (Author, 2022; Capirci & Volterra, 2008; Dupertuis & Moro, 2016;). Even after language, gestures continue playing important cognitive and multimodal communicative roles throughout life (Goldin-Meadow, 2003; Kita et al., 2017). Thus, the study of early gestures has gained attention, as it offers insights into how children intentionally communicate through increasingly complex forms of semiotic mediation in their everyday interactions (Author et al. 2023).

Among children's first gestures, pointing has been studied most frequently (Behne et al., 2012; Fusaro et al., 2014) because of its early developmental role as a main predictor and precursor of language (see review in Kirk et al., 2022 & Kilili-Lesta et al., 2022). Likewise, pointing has been related to early symbolic skills, first joint attention interactions, and the identification of developmental disorders. Nevertheless, doubts remain about the process by which children come to point. These doubts encompass several debates, such as whether pointing is a natural behavior or primarily developed through social interaction (Csibra & Gergely, 2009; Leung & Rheingold, 1981); the role of imitation in this process (Hay & Murray, 1982; Tomasello, 2008); the primacy of cognitive understanding versus social interaction in its emergence (Carpendale & Lewis, 2013; Carpendale et al., 2023; Liszkowski, Carpenter, & Tomasello, 2007; Tomasello, 2008); and whether pointing is the first declarative gesture in development or if there are declarative functions in prior communicative behaviors (Bates et al, 1975; Boundy et al., 2018; Butterworth, 2003), among others.

These debates have led researchers to focus on previous communicative forms that could be pointing's precursors. Among these, ostensive gestures of showing and giving stand out as the first communicative gestures, around 8–10 months (Bates et al., 1975; Reddy, 2008). Ostensive gestures are proximal deictic gestures (Murillo & Belinchón, 2013), in which communication occurs *through* and *about* an object that occupies the child's hand (Eco, 1976; Author et al. 1999). However, we know little about their origin and development (Author et al. 2023), especially in everyday contexts different than the child's home, such as early-years-schools.

Most research on gesture development has been conducted in the home or laboratory. In contrast, children's time in early-years-schools has markedly increased¹, and they are now an everyday interaction context for most children in their first three years. More research is imperative for understanding and optimizing the psychological and educational processes there. Also, studying gesture development within these schools

is interesting since early-years-schools ensure children's active participation in many interactions that differ quantitatively and qualitatively from those in family environments. This has been evidenced in prior studies that have examined symbolic gestures (see review in Valloton, 2008, or Valloton et al., 2014), language development (Bouchard et al., 2010; Degotardi et al., 2016), and joint attention interactions (Cain et al., 2007; Degotardi, 2017) in classroom contexts.

In this article, we aim to describe the developmental process of gestures in early-years-schools. We focus on quantitatively and qualitatively analyzing the development of ostensive gestures, their functions in the infant classroom, and their role in pointing's origins. Below, we describe previous research on the development of ostensive gestures.

1.1. *Ostensive gestures might be pointing's precursors*

In psychology, ostensive gestures have been grouped with pointing and reaching as "deictic gestures" without differentiating their developmental trajectories (Author et al. 2023). Only a few studies have specifically referred to them as gestures of "showing" and "giving" (Bates et al., 1975). This article, however, favors the semiotic term *ostensive gestures*, distinguishing them from other gesture types through the sign–referent relationship. This aligns with the Pragmatics of the Object approach, which argues that objects are foundational elements in communicative acts (Author, 2006).

Semioticians (Eco, 1992; Osolsobè, 1971) remark that, in ostensive gestures, the sign and the referent coincide: The object, which is situated from the beginning in the child's attentional focus, both directs attention and must be attended to (Carpenter, 1998), thus reducing the ambiguity in referent identification. In contrast, more complex pointing gestures imply distance between sign and referent. Pointing requires children to alternate their attention between the pointing person and the distant referent and to establish inferential relationships to link one with the other (Author et al. 2015). This semiotic approach provides a much-needed order and continuity in gesture and communication early development. It allows us to go beyond individual gestures to consider that different gestures, with very different forms and functions, are related in their ways of signifying and sharing meanings. Gesture development thus follows a sequential course from ostensive to indexical gestures and from proximal to distal communication involving objects (Werner & Kaplan, 1963).

In line with these ideas, recent studies have found positive correlations in the frequency of ostensive gestures and subsequent pointing gestures in structured (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015) and semi-structured interactions (Choi et al., 2021;

Manwaring et al., 2017). Therefore, scholars have hypothesized continuity in the referential communicative skills that underlie ostensive and pointing gestures (Author et al. 2023; Puccini et al., 2010).

Correlations by themselves may not be enough to claim a relation between apparently two different forms of communication; however, ostensive and pointing gestures could also maintain a pragmatic relationship analogous to that between pointing and language (Dimitrova et al., 2020; Paradé & Iverson, 2010). That is, communicative functions typically attributed to pointing are already performed earlier and less complexly by ostensive gestures. Among these functions, the imperative – gestures produced to make requests or demand changes in the environment from others - and declarative – gestures that share interest or attention in a referent with others – (Beuker et al., 2013; Boundy et al., 2018; Crais et al., 2004) have taken precedence. However, there is also evidence of interrogative – children using gestures as “questions in action”, seeking information or regulation from the adult in their own actions- (for example, Author, 2009), phatic - gestures with the only objective of prolonging social interactions - (Moreno-Núñez et al., 2017), and positive evaluation (Basilio & Author, 2017) functions – gestures that express approval after an action or accomplishment or positive feedback at the end of an activity -, both in children’s ostensive and pointing gestures.

Elsewhere (see Author et al. 2023), we have described these and other indicators supporting the relationship between ostensive and pointing gestures, such as the frequency of adults’ use of ostensive gestures to communicate and regulate children’s behavior from the first months of life (Jáñez et al., 2021, Zukow-Goldring & Arbib, 2007), or children’s earlier responses to adults’ ostensive gestures than to their pointing (Butterworth, 2003; Juvrud et al., 2019). Likewise, both gestures are altered or absent in communicative developmental disorders (Clements & Chawarska, 2010; Heymann et al., 2018; Mishra et al., 2021), and both are used communicatively in child–adult interactions across Eastern and Western cultures (Fernández-Flecha et al., 2021; Kwon et al., 2018; Salomo & Liszkowski, 2013).

These arguments support the hypothesis that ostensive gestures are semiotically less complex than pointing and enable children to actively participate in rich social triadic exchanges in contact with objects from an early age. This broadens children’s contexts of interaction and facilitates the development of basic referential skills that could be used in later communication at a distance through pointing (Carpenter et al., 1998; Liszkowski, 2008). Early interactions involving ostensive gestures allow children to progressively learn to follow other people’s attentional focus, direct the others’ attention to specific referents, place objects in a shared attentional

framework, and coordinate these skills with other communicative behaviors. Children also acquire greater knowledge about objects and their conventional uses (Author, 2022), creating a shared referential framework that facilitates communication with others (Dimitrova & Moro, 2012).

This leads us to think of ostensive gestures as one of pointing's main precursors. This does not imply that by the time children begin to point, they have fully consolidated knowledge about social interactions. In fact, initial interactions involving pointing gestures are often quite unspecific, identified as "proto-pointings" (see section 1.2.). However, the notion that pointing is not the first communicative mediator children produce indicates that they have some prior experiences to build upon. These foundational skills can later be reconstructed in distal communicative interactions, bridging the gaps necessary for the development of more complex semiotic signs.

1.2. *The progressive development of ostensive gestures*

Gestures are not spontaneously acquired but progressively built in triadic interactions. Transitional behaviors, between actions and gestures, are key to understanding the origins of intentional communication in "pre-conventional" forms (Carpendale et al., 2023; Salter & Carpenter, 2022). These are *proto-gestures*, characterized by: (1) having an ambiguous social function, (2) not occurring predictably in expected social contexts, or (3) not having a morphology that is appropriate to the normative gesture (Dimitrova, 2014; Author et al. 2020).

Several authors have referred to proto-pointing that occurs in contact with objects or with a semi-open hand, generally with imperative functions, and frequently used by younger children and children with atypical development (Cochet & Vauclair, 2010; Liszkowski & Tomasello, 2011; Ramos-Cabo et al., 2022). Likewise, pointing's origin has been linked to previous instrumental uses of the index finger (Kettner & Carpendale, 2018; Paulus et al., 2023), such as reaching attempts (Vygotsky, 1978) or objects' tactile exploration (Shinn, 1975).

There has been less research on ostensive gestures. Some authors have described their conventional morphology (Boundy et al., 2016; Messinger & Fogel, 1998) and functions (Boundy et al., 2018; Moro et al., 2015). Recently, studies have also addressed ostensive gestures' origins, describing changes in their morphology or in the interactions in which they are embedded during the first years (de Bárbaro et al., 2013; Hay & Murray, 1082; Xu et al., 2016). For example, Carpendale et al. (2021) described changes in giving, going from highly structured, adult-guided, "give and take" interactions (Brunner, 1983; Reddy, 2003) to "social acts" initiated and guided by the child. McGregor and Capone (2004) described the development in children's showing

from merely extending objects they were already interacting with to seeking specific objects to share. More recently, Salter and Carpenter (2022) also described changes in ostensive gestures' morphology from pre-conventional to conventional.

1.3. Early-years-schools as a context for gesture development

Gestures and their meanings are rooted in social interactions with others and objects (Carpendale et al., 2023; Torr & Pham, 2016). In consequence, the specific situations where gestures are studied are a defining element of the communicative act (Author, 2009; Hoff, 2006; Orr & Rosenbaum, 2023).

Most research on early gestures has been conducted through structured or semi-structured observations. It is imperative to complement these studies with observations of natural situations (Tamis-LeMonda et al., 2019) in which children are agents and make intentional gestures in real time, adjusted to their needs and abilities, according to their circumstances, to achieve communicative purposes relevant to them. Furthermore, different communicative contexts promote certain gestures to the detriment of others (Olson & Masur, 2011; Puccini et al., 2010). The variability in everyday environments allows us to understand the alternation of different types of gestures that may be masked in controlled situations.

Therefore, children's gestures in early-years-schools could differ from those in parental interactions: (1) While parental interactions involve a one-on-one exchange, in the classroom, one or two adults interact simultaneously with eight children (De Schipper et al., 2006). This may lead to a greater number of communicative behaviors without contingent responses (see Tamis-LeMonda, 2023) and the need to perform more salient behaviors to get the teacher's attention; (2) While parental actions involve different levels of educational intentionality, interactions in the classroom (teachers' actions, activities, spaces and objects) are intentionally designed for education (Gest et al., 2006; Girolametto & Weitzman, 2002). Finally, (3) the presence of other children in the classroom not only increases the number of possible interlocutors but also the types of interaction (e.g., individual vs. group interactions). Children need to adjust their referential skills to communicate with peers and younger children differently than adults. Overall, studying the particularities of gestures' developmental trajectories could be facilitated by the diversity of objects, interlocutors, activities, and social norms posed by early-years-schools.

In this article, we take a longitudinal look at children's ostensive and pointing gestures in early-years-schools during their daily activities. First, we use quantitative–descriptive analysis to explore the relationship between onset age, frequency, and

prevalence of these gestures, as well as their different functions. Then, we complement this with a qualitative–microgenetic analysis of the process of ostensive gesture construction, considering changes in the interactions in which they are embedded and their morphology and functions.

2. METHOD

2.1. Design:

To ensure that the data collected reflected the most natural classroom interactions possible, we conducted a non-participant observational study (Anguera, 2003), focusing on the systematic description of everyday interactions in early-years schools to longitudinally monitor the development of children's gestures over seven months (October to April). This means that the observers remained on the side of the classroom and refrained from interacting with the children or teachers. The study employed a nomothetic approach in order to identify general patterns and principles that apply to all participants.

We followed a mixed and multidimensional methodological data analysis strategy (with multiple response levels) that involved transcription and coding of children's gestures, followed by a quantitative analysis using SPSS to identify general patterns in group measures of frequency and percentage. We then conducted a second-phase qualitative analysis of paradigmatic episodes of interaction. These episodes are specific instances that exemplify the broader patterns of behavior observed, allowing us to provide contextualized interpretations of gestures and their changes throughout the school year. By focusing on these representative episodes and their microgenetic analysis, we were able to gain deeper insights into the development and variation of children's gestures at different moments of the school year.

2.2. Participants:

The participants were infant-classroom children and teachers at three public early-years schools in Madrid, Spain. Schools from three educational districts with high, middle, and low socioeconomic levels were selected. The schools' educational programs were representative of early childhood education in Madrid at the time of the study.

The initial sample size consisted of 29 children. Children ranged from 4 to 8 months at the beginning of the study and from 10 to 14 months at the end. The analysis of gestures was based on each child's age at each observation moment. Specifically, we selected observations between 7 and 13 months, as most children rarely attended

early-years-schools before 6 months old and did not reach 14 months within our observations. Two additional inclusion criteria were established:

- (1) Children must have attended over 50% of the observation sessions (4/7 monthly observations).
- (2) There had to be at least 4 observations per child within the selected age range (7–13 months).

Eight sampled children were excluded because they did not meet these criteria. Therefore, we analyzed the gestures of 21 children (8 girls / 13 boys). Table 1 shows the number of children analyzed by age ($X=15.14$; $SD=2.27$).

Table 1.

Number of children by age and school

Number of children by age				
<i>Age (months)</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>AEarly -yearsB -schoolC</i>		
7	13	4	2	7
8	17	6	6	5
9	14	3	5	6
10	18	7	6	5
11	17	7	5	5
12	15	6	6	3
13		6	4	2
	12			
Mean (SD)	15.14 (2.27)			

In addition to children, three teachers of each group participated in the study. The teachers had a university undergraduate degree in Early Childhood Education and professional experience of more than 10 years in early-years-schools. All participants were Spanish speakers.

2.3. Procedure

The current study was part of a broader project in early-years-schools about the origin of intentional action and communication. The participant schools had a previous relationship with the research group. Before starting the study, informed consent was requested from the families, teachers, and principals of each school.

Observations were carried out monthly by a researcher who visited each classroom for seven months. During these sessions, audiovisual recordings were made of the morning activities organized by the teachers. The teachers were instructed to continue with their usual planning. The filming followed the classrooms' activities. An

activity started when the teacher placed new objects or organized the children and ended when she picked up the objects and reorganized the classroom.

A total of 21 videos were coded with an average duration of 1 hour, 27 minutes (min.=01:14:16; max.=02:20:21; SD=00:19:41). In all observations, the researcher tried to minimize her impact on activities. Priority was given to capturing images with maximum child participation, ensuring a comprehensive data corpus even if a child momentarily left the frame.

2.4. Coding

The children's gestures were transcribed and coded using ELAN software (version 6.7, 2023). Gestures were any motor action the child performed to intentionally communicate something about a referent. For this article, only communicative gestures were analyzed, specifying in each case the recipient: (i) the *teacher*, (ii) *peers*, or (iii) *occasional classroom visitors* (assistant teachers, parents, or observers).

Intentionality was determined based on two primary criteria: (1) the gesture was directed at an interlocutor and assessed through multimodal indicators such as gaze, body posture, physical contact, joint action, and vocalizations. The gaze could occur during, before, or after the gesture. While gaze towards the other person's face, hand, or actions was a key indicator, it was not always necessary. In situations where both interlocutors were already engaged in joint action, gaze might not be needed to establish intentionality. (2) The gesture was about a specific referent, such as an object, event, or action in the classroom. Doubtful cases were clarified with teachers. The behavior was not coded as a gesture if the referent could not be identified.

Additional criteria included (3) persistence, with the child repeating or modifying the gesture if it was initially unsuccessful, and (4) duration, with gestures lasting at least 1 second considered intentional unless accompanied by other communicative behaviors (Iverson & Goldin-Meadow, 2005). Some counterexamples included a child extending their index finger while shaking their arms without directing it at anything, a child pressing a button with their index finger to make a book sound (clarified as a noncommunicative action by a teacher), and a child raising an object to look at it better and then proceeding to suck on it.

The coding procedure included identifying which individual child performed each gesture, their age at the time, the observation moment, and the specific activity during which it occurred. This information enabled us to group gestures by age, regardless of the observation moment, allowing us to perform group analyses while retaining critical information about individual developmental trajectories. Building on previous research (Author et al. 2022; Author, 2009; Author et al. 2007), we categorized gestures

according to their semiotic complexity and type (see Table 2). Only communicative ostensive and indexical gestures were considered; representational (Acredolo & Goodwyn, 1985) and private gestures were excluded (Author, 2022).

Subsequently, based on previous literature, we coded the function of each gesture type by considering the referent, its meaning to the child, and the overall context in which the gesture occurred (Bates et al., 1975; Moreno-Núñez et al., 2017; Murillo & Casla, 2020). Rather than relying on the isolated gesture or its morphology alone, we analyzed the preceding and following events, the material objects involved in the communicative act, and the contextual settings of the gestures.

Children's interactions with objects before and after the gestures, and the specific meanings of these objects within different contexts, were crucial in determining the function of a gesture. For instance, pointing to a spoon that the teacher just removed during mealtime (an imperative function) is very different from pointing to a spoon lying on the ground in the playground (likely a declarative function). The communicative opportunities also varied depending on whether the child had previously learned how to use the spoon (see Author et al. 2017) or if this was a novel object. Moreover, the way the interlocutor interpreted these gestures and the child's reaction were central elements. The child's acceptance, persistence, or modification of their communicative attempt provided key indicators of the gesture's function. In cases of uncertainty, we consulted with the teachers, who provided insights into their interpretations of the gestures and the uses given to the objects children referred to within the classroom.

The aims considered for children's gestures were:

- (1) **Declarative**: to direct the adult's attention to a referent and share an interest in it. These gestures often include alternating attention through gaze, body posture, or physical touch between the referent and the other person, as well as vocalizations and/or positive or interested emotional expressions (Liszkowski, Carpenter, & Tomasello, 2007).

For example, a child might vocalize and show the teacher a rattle they just found in the treasure basket, then continue using it after the teacher smiles and comments.

- (2) **Imperative**: to request, demand, or prompt the adult to change the environment. The child's attention is often focused on their desired object or action (Bates et al., 1975). The child may look for other means to achieve their goals if unanswered. If their initial attempt is unanswered, the child may seek alternative means to achieve their goal.

For instance, if a child fails to put a lid on a can, they may give the lid to the teacher while looking at the can and waiting for her to close it.

- (3) **Phatic**: to maintain a previously initiated interaction, with the focus being on sustaining the communication itself rather than on the specific referents.

However, communication operates with and through the object.

For example, a child may give a building block to the teacher when she tries to leave, but then the child continues playing with their own blocks. Here, the objective is to maintain the interaction rather than to draw attention to the specific building block.

- (4) **Interrogative**: to ask a question, request information about the referent, or seek the adult's direct intervention in the action itself. These gestures often follow interactions where the child has difficulties using an object, encounters a novel object, or attempts to reach an agreement about an adult's proposed activity. Interrogative gestures are the most interactive of all functions, as they require active engagement and response from the adult.

For example, when the teacher asks a child to put a plate in a box, the child tries different actions that are inhibited by the teacher. After these failed attempts, the child shows the plate to the teacher to clarify the referent.

- (5) **Informative**: to share information that the interlocutor does not know. These gestures often arise from open-ended questions posed by the teacher and occur when the child has gained some knowledge of the classroom routine and space.

For example, before reading a book, the teacher might ask, "Where are the books?" and the child points to the bookshelf to inform the teacher.

- (6) **Evaluative**: to share the achievement of an action with another person. These gestures typically occur at the end of an enjoyable activity or when the child feels they have accomplished something (see examples in Basilio & Author, 2017 and Moreno-Llanos et al., 2021)

For instance, a child might clap after the teacher finishes reading a book or extend (ostensive gesture) a building block towards the teacher while smiling after successfully making a tower.

The categories used in this study for gesture types and functions were based on previous research (e.g., Author et al. 2020; Moreno-Núñez et al., 2017). The primary coder was the principal investigator, who coded most of the material. A structured training process was implemented to ensure reliable coding. Initially, the principal investigator and another expert in the field jointly coded 10% of the material, discussing

and resolving any cases of doubt to ensure consistency. Finally, interobserver validation was used to test the reliability of the category system. A second expert, who was partially naïve to the study's objectives but experienced in coding early communicative interactions, coded 25% of the footage that had not been previously reviewed. A high level of agreement was obtained using Cohen's Kappa: 86% agreement for the type of gesture ($k=.86, N=111$) and 81% for the function ($k=.819, N=111$).

Table 2.

Coding categories: Gestures' semiotic complexity and types

PLEASE, INSERT HERE TABLE 2

3. RESULTS

In this study, to identify relationships between the development of ostensive and pointing gestures, we descriptively analyzed the total number of gestures in the classroom and observed changes in their types and functions according to children's age. Then, we qualitatively analyzed age-related interaction variations involving ostensive gestures.

For group results, we refer to the observations of the 21 participants by their specific ages at different times. In the following analysis, the data grouped for each age come from different observation periods for each child. For example, not all participants were 8 months old at the same time (or at the same observation), so the analysis was conducted using the data from each participant when they were 8 months old, regardless of the specific observation session in which it occurred. Gestures were analyzed per child, considering their individual trajectories, and then grouped by age. This method allowed us to account for participant characteristics and provide a comprehensive analysis that reflects both group trends and individual differences.

3.1. Total number of gestures in the classroom

The first gestures were observed when children reached 8 months. Of the 21 participants, all but one made gestures throughout the study's duration. In total, 865 gestures were recorded. 82% (708 gestures) were directed at the teacher, while only 5% (40) at classmates. The remaining 13% (117) were directed at other people (auxiliary teachers, parents, or observers).

We applied the Wilcoxon non-parametric sign test to assess differences in the total frequency of gestures. The number of gestures produced by children in the classroom when they were between 8 and 10 months old averaged 5 gestures per child (SD = 5.74; min=0; max=21). This was significantly lower than the number of gestures produced between 11 and 13 months, which averaged 34 gestures per child (SD = 47.11; min=1; max=159; $Z = -3.462$, $p = .001$). Monthly comparisons revealed significant increases in gesture frequency only between 11 months (M = 21.19; SD = 25.15) and 12 months (M = 8.5; SD = 12.9), indicating a progressive increase in gesture use. However, this trend was not observed between 12 and 13 months. This lack of a significant increase may be due to the reduced sample size rather than a plateau in gesture production.

Through the study, children's gestures became more frequent and varied in type and function. Overall, ostensive gestures, comprising 45% of all gestures (349/772), were the most common. These primarily included showing at all ages, accounting for 68% (239/349) of the ostensive gestures analyzed, with giving also observed. In successive analyses, both types of ostensive gestures were grouped together to understand the differences between proximal and distal forms of communication. Conventional pointing made up 30% (235) of the gestures analyzed, and other pointing types accounted for 24% (188).

Then, we proceeded to analyze the changes in the types and functions of gestures with age.

3.2. *Gesture types in the classroom by children's age*

First, gestures were analyzed by type, allowing us to observe changes in the gestural repertoire of the classroom with age.

3.2.1. *Group frequency of gesture type by age*

The descriptive group analysis of classroom gesture frequency by age (see Figure 1) revealed that *at 8 months*, ostensive gestures predominated, representing 94% of the gestures observed at that age (29/31). Only in exceptional cases were proto-pointing and touch-pointing observed (6%; 2 gestures). When children were *between 9 to 10 months*, ostensive gestures frequency significantly increased (9–10 months: $Z=2.48$, $p<.05$; 10–11 months: $Z=2.75$, $p<.05$), comprising 59% at 9 months (16/27 gestures), and 54% at 10 months (34/63). However, their gesture repertoire began to diversify when they reached 10 months. Proto-pointing and touch-pointing reached 40% (25/63) of the gestures, surpassing conventional pointing (6%; 4/63).

Figure 1.

Percentage of children's gestures by age (months)

From 11 to 12 months, ostensive and all types of pointing gestures were observed at similar frequencies in the classroom. Ostensive gestures ranged from 47% (71/152) at 11 months to 36% (128/354) at 12 months. Conventional pointing increased progressively and significantly ($Z=2.81$; $p<.05$), from 34% (51/152) at 11 months to 44% (154/354) at 12 months. Pointing coexisted with its proto-conventional form even at 13 months. A decreasing trend was not identified in proto-pointing nor in touchpointing. By 13 months, children's gestural repertoire balanced between indexical (53%) and ostensive (47%) gestures.

3.2.2. Onset age and number of children performing each type of gesture

Children varied in when they started performing different gesture types, showing progressive development (see Figure 2). To examine significant differences in mean onset ages for each gesture type, we used Wilcoxon's non-parametric test, appropriate due to the non-normal age distribution for ostensive gestures (Shapiro $Z=0.769$; $p<0.05$). First, we compared the average onset age of ostensive gestures with that of conventional pointing, revealing that ostensive gestures began significantly earlier ($Z=2.701$; $p<.05$). On average, children produced ostensive gestures from 9.7 months ($SD=1.42$), with 62% of the participants (13/21 children at 10 months) making their first ostensive gesture by then. In contrast, conventional pointing began later, around 11 months ($SD=1.16$), and was less common, as only 33% (7) of the children had pointed by then.

Proto-pointing apparently followed a developmental path between ostensive and pointing gestures. However, significant differences in onset ages were only observed

with ostensive gestures ($Z=2.06$; $p<.05$), not with pointing. Proto-pointing began later than ostensive gestures, around 10.63 months ($SD=1.5$), but cannot be confirmed to precede conventional pointing. By 11 months, 62% (13) of children used proto-pointing in the classroom.

Similarly, significant differences in onset ages were also found for ostensive gestures and touch-pointing ($Z=1.956$; $p=.05$), with touch-pointing starting around 11 months ($SD=1.48$). No significant differences were found with other forms of pointing.

Figure 2.

Number of children performing each type of gesture by age (Cumulative frequencies)

* --- = Mean onset age

Children showed more ostensive than indexical gestures in the first year. By 12 months old, 91% (20) had made at least one ostensive gesture, while only 41% (9) pointed. However, the number of children who pointed rose to 45% (10 children) by 13 months. Proto-pointing was also frequent by then, performed by 59% (13) of children at

12 months and 68% (15) at 13 months. This suggests a developmental shift from proximal to increasingly complex distal communication. Touch-pointing was performed by 52% (11) of children at 13 months, mirroring the trend in conventional pointing.

3.2.3. Individual differences in ostensive gestures and pointing production

While general patterns in gesture development were evident, individual differences also emerged (see Figure 3). Considering the varied onset ages for different gestures, we focused on their acquisition order. Most children (86%; 18/21) made ostensive gestures before pointing, 81% (17) before touch-pointing, and 57% (12) before proto-pointing. No child used conventional pointing before ostensive gestures. However, 10% (2) made ostensive and pointing gestures simultaneously. Likewise, 38% (8) performed proto-pointings concurrently with or before ostensive gestures, and 15% (3) did so before or alongside touch-pointing.

Figure 3.

Individual differences in gesture's onset age and trajectories

Additionally, 48% of children (10) performed proto-pointing before pointing conventionally, while 29% (6) alternated between these gestures from the same age. Touch-pointing displayed a diverse trend. An equal number of children performed touch-pointing before, simultaneously with, and after conventional pointing (14%; 3 children in each case), and the same number of children (19%; 4 children each) did so alongside and after proto-pointing.

Only one child (5%) did not perform ostensive gestures throughout the observations. In contrast, touch-pointing was not used by 48% (10 children), protopointing by 19% (4), and pointing by 48% (10).

3.2.4. *Relationship between the frequency of ostensive and pointing gestures*

We examined the relationship between ostensive and pointing gestures' total frequency correlation. Spearman's correlation coefficient was used because the distribution was significantly far from normal. A moderate, positive, and significant correlation (Spearman's $\rho=.772$; $p<.05$) was found, suggesting that higher use of ostensive gestures in the classroom coincided with more frequent conventional pointing.

Additionally, we correlated the frequency of pointing at its onset age with the frequency of ostensive gestures at that age and earlier. For example, if a child started pointing at 12 months, the frequency of their pointing was correlated with (1) the frequency of their ostensive gestures at 12 months and (2) the sum of the frequency of their ostensive gestures in previous months. We only considered children who performed both gestures before 13 months ($N= 11$). A significant, positive, and moderate correlation (Spearman's $\rho=.664$; $p< .05$) was found between the frequency of both gestures in the same month. This implies that, as children began pointing, they also made ostensive gestures. Likewise, a significant, negative, and moderate correlation (Spearman's $\rho=-.657$; $p< .05$) was found with the frequency of previous months' ostensive gestures, indicating that the first pointing gestures were infrequent but increased over time, following a period of high ostensive gesture frequency.

3.3. *Gestures' functions by age*

In the second phase, we analyzed the functions of different gesture types. The majority (51%) served a declarative function (444 gestures), while 39% (338) were imperative (see Table 3). Less common functions included: phatic (5.3%; 46), informative (2.7%; 23), interrogative (1.4%; 12), and, rarely, evaluation functions (0.2%; 2). All gesture types had declarative, imperative, and interrogative functions. Phatic and

evaluative functions were exclusive to ostensive gestures, and informative functions were only observed in pointing gestures.

Table 3.

Frequency of children's gesture functions

Functions	Gesture Types	Age Range ^d (Mean; SD)	F	Total (%)
<i>Declarative</i>	Ost ^a	8–12 (9.95; 1.39)	202	444 (51.3%)
	Pointing	9–13 (11; 1.26)	122	
	PP ^b	9–13 (10.82; 1.33)	56	
	TP ^c	8–13 (11.46; 1.51)	64	
<i>Imperative</i>	Ost	8–13 (10.92; 1.78)	105	338 (39.1%)
	Pointing PP	10–13 (11.25; .89)	137	
		9–13 (10.64; 1.45)	71	
	TP	10–13 (11.67; 1.37)	25	
<i>Phatic</i>	Ost	8–12 (9.44; 1.42)	46	46 (5.3%)
<i>Informative</i>	Pointing	10–12 (11; 1)	7	23 (2.7%)
	PP	10–12 (11; 1)	4	
	TP	12–13 (12.67; .58)	12	
<i>Interrogative</i>	Ost	10–11 (10.67; .58)	3	12 (1.4%)
	Pointing PP	12	5	
		13	2	
	TP	13	2	
<i>Evaluative</i>	Ost	11	2	2 (0.2%)
			<i>Total</i>	865

^a Ost. = Ostensive gestures; ^b PP = Proto-Pointing; ^c TP = Touch-Pointing; ^d Age in months

Declarative and imperative functions emerged first in development (at 8 months in ostensive gestures and at 9–10 months in pointing types). Ostensive gestures also had phatic functions from 8 months, while pointing gestures showed informative functions from 9 months. Interrogative functions emerged at 10 months in ostensive gestures and 12–13 months in pointing and proto-pointing. An evaluation function, albeit rare, was observed in ostensive gestures from 12 months.

Given that declarative and imperative functions predominated in the classroom gesture repertoire, we focused on their developmental trajectories. While 95% (20) of children performed ostensive gestures with declarative functions by the end of their first year, only 33% (7) performed pointing (Figs. 4A & 4B). Differences were less pronounced for imperative functions: 48% (10) used imperative ostensive gestures by 12 months old, and 43% (9) used imperative pointing. By then, touch-pointing was used for declarative functions by 38% (8) of children and for imperative functions by 19% (4)

(Fig. 4C). Finally, 48% (10) of children used proto-pointing (10) for declarative and 62% (13) for imperative functions at 12 months (Fig. 4D).

Through a non-parametric Wilcoxon sign test, we found significant differences between the total number of ostensive ($Z=2.819$; $p<.05$) and touch-pointing ($Z=-2.1$; $p<.05$) gestures when comparing declarative and imperative functions. Declarative functions predominated in both cases. Such differences were not observed in protopointing and pointing gestures.

Figure 4.
Gesture's types and functions by age

*Legend: Type_Function / Types: Ost = Ostensive Gestures, Point = Pointing, TP = Touch-Pointing, PP = Proto-Pointing / Functions: Dcl = Declarative, Imp = Imperative.

3.4. *Changes in teacher–child interactions involving ostensive gestures by age*

The development of children's gestures extended beyond frequency and onset age, encompassing changes in the interactions in which gestures were embedded as well as in their morphology, functions, and complexity. These were discernible through descriptive analysis of interactions. We selected four observations that accounted for most of the changes observed in teacher–child interactions involving ostensive gestures (two of giving and two of showing), in which the target child appeared in the foreground. Two represent the 8–10-month period, and two the 11–13-month period.

Observations 1 and 2 exemplify early ostensive gestures between 8–10 months, characterized by three main aspects: (1) there were motor challenges in their morphology, similar to the ones in proto-pointing. In ostensive gestures of giving, children struggled with directing objects toward the teacher's hand, often releasing them prematurely or needing adult support to release them. Difficulties in ostensive gestures of showing included partial arm extensions, using both hands for stability, object wobbling (falling out of the interlocutor's visual field), and brief durations under 3 seconds; (2) Teachers often prompted and scaffolded these ostensive gestures, either directly or indirectly. As shown in Observation 1, ostensive gestures of giving were framed within structured give-and-take interactions (similar to those described by Reddy, 2008), initiated and led by the teacher. The teacher repeatedly asked for the object using various semiotic mediators, such as "give me" and nodding gestures, verbalizations, smiling, and sometimes gently touching or pulling the object. These prompts continued until the child engaged in the interaction. Additionally, the teacher adjusted the morphology of the child's gesture when necessary, moving her hand closer to the child and helping her release the object. Ostensive gestures of showing typically happened when the teacher engaged with children's actions, such as commenting, looking, or smiling at them, prompting children to extend objects towards her (Observation 2); (3) ostensive gestures often lacked a specific response expectation. Observation 1 is a paradigmatic example of a phatic function in a child's ostensive gesture of giving, aimed merely at prolonging the interaction with the teacher without any other goal. The child does not attempt to use the object between turns, and the interaction with both the teacher and the object ends when the teacher's attention shifts. In observation 2, ostensive gestures of showing are declarative, aimed at sharing the rhythmic-sound use of a rattle. However, the child readily accepts the teacher's first response, which is unrelated to his object extension and use, and does not intend to prolong the interaction.

Observation 1.

Structured "give-and-take" interaction: Ostensive gesture of giving (8 months)

PLEASE INSERT HERE OBSERVATION 1

Observation 2.

Sharing an object use: Ostensive gestures of showing (8 months)

PLEASE INSERT HERE OBSERVATION 2

These characteristics change progressively during the first year of life. By 11–13 months, children can initiate gestures and respond to others through gestures. Communication has also become a goal, relating it to specific referents. Children actively select, extend, and exchange objects that are of interest to them. In addition, their gestures become more complex and serve distinct communicative functions (e.g., initiating games or joint uses of objects, asking questions, giving information, etc.). This advancement is evident in their persistent efforts to elicit particular responses from others, their emotional reactions to the outcomes of their gestures, and their flexible use of various strategies to share meanings.

Observation 3 illustrates an 11-month-old girl independently producing ostensive gestures of giving during a "treasure basket" activity. Two elements are highlighted in this observation: the child's persistence and the adjustments in her gesture to share with the teacher a specific object of interest—a can (see Boundy et al. 2018 for examples in experimental situations). Sharing the can is difficult for the girl since the teacher initially ignores her. To achieve her goal, she persists in her gesture and resorts to different strategies: (1) *repeats* the gesture multiple times, (2) *moves* the object to make it more salient, (3) *brings* the object closer to the teacher's hand, and (4) *makes physical contact* with the teacher. When these fail, the child employs a more complex approach involving an initial separation between means and ends (Piaget, 1936/1952): to overcome an obstacle (the distance from the teacher), she temporarily pauses her goal (halts her gesture) and initiates a different action that is difficult for her (she repositions herself for better access) before resuming her goal. She repeats the ostensive gesture, this time placing the object at the teacher's eye level, finally getting the desired response. The interaction concludes following the teacher's response.

Observation 3.

Ostensive gestures, persistence, and adjustment to obstacles (11 months)

PLEASE INSERT HERE OBSERVATION 3

Finally, observation 4 captures the persistence and specific purpose of an 11-month-old child's gestures aimed at initiating joint book reading (an imperative function). Over 10 minutes, the child flexibly switches between touch-pointing and ostensive gestures of giving when the teacher is near and attentive, and showing gestures when she moves away or engages with other children (see Figure 5). Unlike earlier ostensive gestures, these are always multimodal, combined with vocalizations and eye contact with the teacher. The child's self-determination is evident as he persists in his gestures, not content with just any verbal response from the teacher or with the reading of any other book. He continues with his gestures until he achieves a particular activity based on his own choice and past experiences with the object.

Observation 4.

Different gesture types and referent specificity: Ostensive gestures and touch-pointing (13 months)

PLEASE INSERT HERE OBSERVATION 4

Figure 5.

Microgenetic analysis of observation 4.

4. DISCUSSION

This research studied the development of first gestures in early-years-schools, a context mostly unknown in early communication investigations. Our focus was on the frequency, onset age, prevalence, social functions, and interaction contexts of

ostensive gestures, as well as their link to the subsequent emergence of complex forms of distal communication, such as pointing.

Children communicated frequently through gestures in the infant classroom. First intentional gestures began as early as 8 months and increased progressively in frequency and diversity with age. By the first year's end, children demonstrated a balanced use of ostensive and indexical gestures with different communicative functions. Both gesture types coexisted in development. Children tailored them to the context, choosing the most suitable gesture to effectively convey different meanings in increasingly diverse situations (Author et al. 2020). We observed that communicating with teachers about objects progressively became a goal for children. To accomplish it, children persisted in their gestures, adjusted them to obstacles, and adapted them to changes in interactive situations.

Overall, gesture development followed an ostensive–indexical / proximal–distal course despite individual differences. Ostensive gestures of showing and giving were the classrooms' first and most common gestures. This is likely due to the careful selection of engaging, challenging, and age-appropriate materiality that characterizes early-years-schools. Ostensive gestures remained relevant throughout the first year, coexisting with more semiotically complex gestures. These results situate ostensive gestures as key to understanding gestures' origins and, in turn, the origin of intentional communication.

Notably, there were more ostensive gestures of showing than giving during all the observations. This might be explained by giving's later development than showing, although previous research challenges this idea (Carpendale et al., 2021). A fitting explanation might be the classroom setting. Unlike typical parent–child interactions where the adult is fully attentive and proximate to the child, children share the teacher's attention with seven other children in the classroom. Thus, showing gestures, which can bridge distances between interlocutors and initiate interactions without immediate adult response, become more practical than giving gestures, which require closer proximity and active reciprocation (Author et al. 2023; Marcos et al., 2003). In fact, when ostensive giving gestures went unanswered, they were coded as showing, given the difficulty of discerning the child's initial intent without actual object exchange.

Furthermore, our findings support the hypothesis of ostensive gestures as one of pointing's precursors. Firstly, ostensive gestures appeared significantly earlier and were more common among children throughout the first year. These were gestures semiotically less complex than pointing. Secondly, in line with previous studies, we found a moderate correlation in the frequency of ostensive and pointing gestures produced in the same and previous months. Thirdly, while individual differences were

found in gestures' developmental path, no child began pointing before producing ostensive gestures, though some started them simultaneously. Further research with larger samples is needed for conclusive insights into these developmental trajectories. These results alone may be insufficient to support a relationship between ostensive gestures and pointing. However, in addition to the cumulative prior research leading in this direction (e.g., Author, 2009; Bates et al., 1975; Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Carpenter, 1978; Choi et al., 2021; Puccini et al., 2010; Salomo & Liszkowski, 2013), we also found a functional/pragmatic continuity between the two gestures, parallel to the one present between pointing and language. Ostensive gestures performed declarative, imperative, and interrogative functions from an early age, which were later observed in children's pointing gestures. Furthermore, while ostensive and pointing gestures' underlying referential skills might be related, each also has pragmatic specificities that complement each other.

The results of this study provide further evidence supporting the contribution of early interactions involving ostensive gestures to the development of distal communication through pointing, acting as their precursors. However, this does not imply that ostensive gestures are the *only* factor in the origins of pointing or that the transition from proximal to distal communication is straightforward. Instead, our hypothesis aligns with other existing theories about how pointing develops. For instance, while we have not provided direct evidence on this, we acknowledge that parents' and teachers' use of pointing gestures in various situations to communicate with children and regulate their actions, making them more noticeable behaviors and clearer for them (see, for example, the use of touch-pointing and multiple pointing by parents in Basilio & Author, 2017; and by teachers during book-reading in Contin & Author et al. 2021), might be fundamental in explaining how pointing emerges.

We also align with the process-relational approach based on Mead's (1934) perspective, which emphasizes the role of adults' interpretations of children's early uses of their index fingers as communicative intents from the beginning. These repeated adult "overinterpretations" help children understand the impact of their actions on others, gradually encouraging them to use these actions more referentially (Kettner & Carpendale, 2018; Carpendale et al., 2023). This process likely also plays a role in the origins of ostensive gestures, as observation 1 suggests. Regarding pointing development, the role of ostensive gestures as precursors is central to this approach, as it helps explain the gradual nature of its development. Children's previous experiences with rich and enjoyable referential communication through less complex semiotic systems, such as ostensive gestures, provide an ideal steppingstone for this process to build upon. The foundational skills and common ground acquired through

ostensive gestures would bridge the gap created by the distance between sign and referent characteristic of pointing gestures, thereby facilitating its referential use.

Regarding pointing gesture development, these gestures emerged in the classroom when children reached 11 months and became more frequent by the year's end. The persistent and frequent observation of "proto-pointing" alongside conventional pointing suggests that pointing is a complex sign that builds *progressively*. This development is not necessarily linear but varies in morphology and functions during object-oriented social interactions. On the other hand, touch-pointing, less ambiguous for referent identification, followed a developmental path similar to conventional pointing. It was used communicatively from 11 months and became more frequent by 13 months. Previous studies have reported its frequent use by teachers in early childhood education and by parents during problem-solving situations (Author et al. 2021; Author et al. 2005). Touch-pointing may not be less complex than conventional pointing. Instead, it may serve specific alternative functions in early-life interactions, which should be addressed in future research.

This study also examined classroom gestures' communicative functions. Declarative and imperative functions were most common, but around 12–13 months, more complex functions, such as interrogative, informative, and evaluative, appeared, albeit infrequently. Investigating such functions in older children within early-years/schools settings remains an open research area. Notably, declarative and imperative functions were distinctly observed only in proximal communication forms (ostensive and touch-pointing gestures), with declarative being more frequent. These differences may also be found in pointing gestures later in development (Ramos-Cabo et al., 2022). Declarative functions have played a pivotal role in early communicative development research, marking the initial emergence of referential acts (Camaioni, 1997). The prominence of declarative functions in early proximal communication challenges traditional views that downplay their significance as closer to actions than gestures (Author et al. 2023). Instead, it highlights the importance of proximal communication and reconsidering the role of objects as defining elements in early communicative development (Clark, 2003).

The qualitative and microgenetic analysis of interactions involving ostensive gestures revealed transitional forms in children's early attempts around 8–10 months old, resembling proto-pointing in their morphological variability and less specific interaction-focused functions. Employing an interactive approach to study early gestures proved insightful, highlighting changes in: (1) teachers' roles and scaffolding strategies; (2) the child's increasing response requirements, persistence, and gesture adaptation in difficult situations; and (3) the meaning of objects for the interactive

partners, making the child more interested in the particularity of their uses and the teacher more accurate in her interpretations of children intentions. Further research should closely examine the construction process of ostensive gestures during everyday interactions, focusing on both changes in gestures' morphology and functions, as well as in their interactive contexts.

The study also found differences between gestures directed at teachers and peers. This result is striking when considering the 8:1 child-to-teacher ratio in classrooms. Gesture disparity could arise from peers' often not responding contingently, either from misunderstanding or inattention. It is noteworthy that, although infrequent, gestures *between* peers were already present in the infant classroom. Daily interactions with peers not only create a more defiant communicative context for trying to get the adult's attention but also create unique communicative opportunities. In fact, teachers often encouraged peer interactions, which involved observation and imitation of others' actions, parallel or joint object use, and conflict resolution over object possession (Moreno-Llanos et al., 2023). Future investigations on peer interactions should examine these early exchanges around objects, which may lay the foundations for later social and communicative skills.

Despite managing multiple children, teachers paid close attention to each child's actions, giving them space and opportunities to be intentional agents, progressively taking more initiative to act and communicate. Teacher's specific interventions engaged children with challenges and constantly provided contingent responses to their gestures. These responsive behaviors imbued children's gestures with meaning and encouraged diverse communication efforts. Teachers' scaffolding in the classroom allows children's actions to transition from proto-conventional to conventional communication gestures with a diversity of functions. This notion has been proposed in previous studies for more complex gestures. For example, Author et al. (2020) describe an observation where the teacher "corrects" the proto-gesture of a child who tries to wave at a puppet. It has also been proposed in different studies for ostensive gesture development (Carpendale et al., 2023), and, in this paper, it has been illustrated in observation 1, where the teacher promotes a communicative interaction through a "give me" gesture and scaffolds the child's imprecise object extension into a give-and-take communicative situation. Here, the child plays an active role, engages both with the teacher and the object, and shows signs of enjoyment (an important factor for further communicative development; see Reddy, 2008). Investigating teachers' strategies to enhance children's communicative attempts is an important area for future research.

In conclusion, this study underscores the key role of ostensive gestures in early intentional communication across everyday interactions and their relationship with

pointing. Our results enhance the understanding of early communicative development and provide valuable insights into understanding the origins of intentional communication before pointing and language. Intentional communication may begin in early communicative exchanges through and about objects. By elucidating the nuances of gesture development in classroom settings, our findings suggest the importance of children's participation in environments that support gesture-rich interactions with diverse objects in diverse social situations. Overall, this study paves the way for future exploration of the intricate dynamics of early intentional communication in educational contexts.

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Table 2.

Coding categories: Gestures' semiotic complexity and types

<i>Semiotic complexity</i>	Coding Categories	<i>Types of Gesture</i>
<p>Ostensive Gestures</p> <p>Homomateric: The object shown or given is both sign and referent. Communication is proximal, through the referent.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ostensive Gesture - Show</i></p> <p>Children extend an object towards another person, placing it in her visual field, to communicate something about it, typically involving eye contact.</p> <p><i>A 13-month-old child shows a sound bottle to the teacher to share interest</i> (Declarative function)</p>	
	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Ostensive Gesture - Giving</i></p> <p>Children extend an object towards another person, placing it in her hand or lap, to communicate something about it.</p> <p><i>A 9-month-old child gives a sound bottle to the teacher, initiating a give-and-take game</i> (Phatic function)</p>	
<p>Ostensive/Indexical Gestures</p> <p>Heteromateric: There is differentiation between sign and referent. Communication is proximal, in contact with the referent.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Touch-pointing</i></p> <p>Children indicate an object by touching it with an extended index finger and the rest of the hand closed or partially closed.</p> <p><i>A 13-month-old child and vocalizes and touches a is</i></p>	
<p>Indexical Gestures</p> <p>Heteromateric: There is differentiation between sign and referent. Communication is distal, including the present referent but at a distance.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Proto-pointing</i></p> <p>A precursor to conventional pointing. Children indicate an object with the index finger extended, but with variations: a partially opened hand, an unextended or unstable arm, or the hand opening and closing.</p> <p><i>A 10-month-old child requests a peer's pacifier from the teacher by pointing with a half-open hand without reaching for it</i> (Imperative function).</p>	

Conventional Pointing

Children indicate a referent by extending an arm and index finger towards it, keeping the rest of the hand closed.

A 10-month-old child points to a glass in response to the teacher's query, "Where's the glass?"
(Informative function).

Observation 1.

Structured "give-and-take" interaction: *Ostensive gesture of giving (8 months)*

School B – Free Play

Child (C): 0;8;17 / Teacher (T)

Duration: 00:00:27

Gesture: Ostensive – Giving

Function: Phatic

T reaches out and asks C for the object she is holding ("Give it to me"), while opening and closing her hand.

C alternates her gaze between T's hand and face.

C extends the object towards T's hand (*ostensive gesture – give*).

When T reaches out to pick it up, C smiles.

T offers the object back to C: "Take it, it's for you" (*ostensive gesture – give*).

C looks at the object before picking it up.

T and C exchange the object three additional times. T adjusts C's gesture when it does not reach her hand or when C does not let go of the object.

Observation 2.

Sharing an object use: Ostensive gestures of showing (8 months)

School A – Sound Objects
 Child (C): 0;8;3 / Teacher (T)
 Duration: 00:00:20

Gesture: Ostensive – Show
Function: Declarative (to share the use of O)

C makes a rhythmic-sound use with a rattle.

T watches him and smiles.

C looks at T and extends the rattle towards her (*ostensive gesture – showing*).

T looks at C and smiles at him.

C moves the rattle while showing it, varying the extension of his arm.

T continues to look at C and smile.

The sequence ends when C lets go of the rattle while continues to look at T, who interacts with another child. C starts sucking on the rattle (non-conventional use).

Observation 3.*Ostensive gestures, persistence, and adjustment to obstacles (11 months)*

School B – Treasure Basket
 Child (C): 0;11;18 / Teacher (T)
 Duration: 00:00:48.

Gesture: Ostensive – Give
Function: Declarative

C takes a can from the floor and explores it.

C turns around, looks at T, and extends her arm towards her while holding the can (*Ostensive gesture – give*).

T does not answer C's gesture.

While holding the can, C moves her arm from side to side to make her gesture more noticeable.

T takes a tissue to wipe C's nose.

C takes advantage of T's proximity to direct the can to her hand (*ostensive gesture – give*).

T does not answer C's gesture.

C leans on the table to stand up with slight difficulty, then retakes the can and extends it to T while making eye contact (*ostensive gesture – give*).

T smiles and places her hand to receive the can (*representational gesture*).

C places the can on T's hand and looks at it (*ostensive gesture – give*)

The sequence ends when T smiles and places the can in front of C. Then, C takes it back and continues its exploration.

Observation 4.

Different gesture types and referent specificity: Ostensive gestures and touch-pointing (13 months)

School A – Books

Child (C): 0;13;19 / Teacher (T)

Duration: 00:10:39

Gestures: Ostensive – Show and Give / Touch-pointing

Function: Imperative

C looks at T and points to a book he wants to read while vocalizing (*touch-pointing*).

T replies: "Yes, it's the little birds."

*C repeats touch-pointing with verbalizations 3 times

C looks at T and extends the book towards her while making eye contact and vocalizing (*ostensive gesture – give*)

T takes the book and gives C another book.

C rejects the new book and retrieves the first one.

Even when T moves away, C keeps making multiple *ostensive gestures of showing*, accompanied by gaze and vocalizations.

*C makes 3 *ostensive gestures of showing* with one or two arms. There are variations in the height at which he holds the book.

When T starts reading another book with all the children, C continues to *show* the initial book.

T looks at C and replies, "Yes, the little birds, open it yourself."

*C repeats *ostensive gestures of showing* 6 times

C makes a new *ostensive gesture of giving*.

T says: "Let's see how you open it? I'll help you," reaches over, and grabs the book.

T begins reading the book with C.
